

New Metal Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with Some Thiosemicarbazide Derivatives

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The metal complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with 1-isobutyryl-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (IBTS) and 1-(2,4-dinitro)-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (PNTS) have been prepared and characterized by conventional chemical and physical measurements. The stereochemistry of the complexes has been studied with the help of magnetic and spectral measurements. The anomalous magnetic moments observed in Cu(II) bromide complexes have been explained. The infrared spectral studies have been used to determine the bonding sites in the complexes.

In continuation of our earlier work on the ligands containing thiosemicarbazide moiety¹⁻³ and in view of the studies of Aggarwal *et al.*³⁻⁵, we extend our studies to investigate both 1-isobutyryl-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide and 1-(2,4-dinitro)-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide and their complexes with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II).

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by slowly adding the appropriate volume of phenyl isothiocyanate to isobutyric acid hydrazide and/or 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in absolute ethanol. The mixtures were refluxed on a water bath till precipitation was complete. The products were filtered off, recrystallized from absolute ethanol and finally dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Purity was checked by elemental analysis.

Preparation of the complexes: The solid complexes of IBTS and PNTS were prepared by mixing equimolar amounts of metal salt and ligand in absolute ethanol. The mixtures were refluxed on a water bath for about 1 hr. The complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II), derived from IBTS, were prepared using the same procedure in presence of sodium acetate as a buffering agent. The isolated solid complexes were filtered off, washed several times with hot ethanol and diethylether respectively and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. No more than *bis*-ligand complexes were obtained even in the presence of an excess of ligand.

Analyses: Carbon and hydrogen contents were determined in the Microanalytical Unit of the National Research Centre, Cairo. Halides and metal contents were determined by standard methods⁶.

Physical measurements: Molar conductivities were measured on Phillips PR 9500 and Tacussel CD 6NG conductivity bridges. Infrared spectra were measured on Perkin Elmer 557 using CsI optics with dried nujol mull. The electronic spectra of the solid complexes were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 700C spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed by Gouy method. All measurements were carried out at Liverpool University, U.K.

Results and Discussion

All the solid complexes are stable in air and soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in other organic solvents. Molar conductivities in DMF at 25° are in the range 11.4-46 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Analytical data are listed in Table 1.

Infrared spectra: The bonding sites in the complexes have been determined by a careful comparison of the infrared spectra of the solid complexes with those of IBTS and PNTS and by considering our earlier work^{1,2}. The ligands can exist in the tautomeric forms (I) and (II).

The infrared spectra showed that both PNTS and IBTS exist mainly in the thioketo form (I). The strong bands in the region 3090-3380 cm⁻¹ in

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND EFFECTIVE MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF PNTS AND IBTS COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis %								λ_m in DMF	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Found				(Calcd.)					
			O	H	M	X	O	H	M	X		
IBTS	White	158	55.52	6.31	—	—	55.56	6.39	—	—	—	—
[Cu(IBTS-H)Cl] 2H ₂ O	Grey	169	36.29	4.68	17.65	9.94	35.58	4.88	17.11	9.55	24.00	1.86
[Cu(IBTS-H)Br] 3H ₂ O	Grey	160	29.54	4.46	15.09	18.02	30.46	4.56	14.65	18.42	46.00	1.26
[Cu(IBTS-H) ₂] 2H ₂ O	Violet	204	46.72	4.67	11.22	—	46.18	5.64	11.10	—	21.00	2.36
[Cu(IBTS) ₂ SO ₄]	Black	170	41.94	4.35	9.86	—	41.66	4.77	10.02	—	23.00	2.32
[Co(IBTS-H) ₂] 2H ₂ O	Brown	270	46.66	5.04	10.65	—	46.55	5.68	10.38	—	36.00	4.93
[Ni(IBTS-H) ₂] 2H ₂ O	Brown	360	46.43	5.42	10.27	—	46.55	5.68	10.35	—	24.00	2.81
PNTS	Yellow	183	46.02	3.98	—	—	46.59	3.90	—	—	—	—
[Cu(PNTS-H)Br]	Brown	158	33.09	2.40	16.39	13.41	32.68	2.53	16.72	13.30	16.20	0.69
[Cu(PNTS-H) ₂]	Brown	167	42.63	2.89	—	8.37	42.65	3.90	—	8.68	11.40	0.96
[Ni(PNTS-H) ₂]	Black	174	42.65	3.24	—	8.16	42.93	3.32	—	8.07	20.00	Diamag.
[Co(PNTS-H) ₂] H ₂ O	Black	162	41.89	3.36	—	7.81	41.88	3.51	—	7.90	23.50	2.10
[Cu(PNTS) ₂ SO ₄]	Brown	171	37.72	3.26	—	7.83	37.61	3.16	—	7.66	12.50	2.01

the spectra of the ligands, assigned to ν NH vibrations are shifted to lower wavenumbers in all complexes except copper sulphate complexes. The shift of these bands suggests the involvement of at least one of the NH groups in coordination. This is supported by the presence of a band in the region 370-390 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})^{\nu}$ and the small positive shifts of the band in the region 1040-1070 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})^{\nu}$.

The bands in the regions 1280-1290 cm^{-1} and 770-780 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ with a contribution of $\nu(\text{CN})$. The disappearance of these bands in the spectra of all the complexes (except copper sulphate complexes) with simultaneous appearance of a new band in the region 620-690 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})^{10}$ could be taken as an evidence of the ligands coordinating via thioenol structure. Also, the appearance of a new band in the region 1540-1580 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in the spectra of complexes could be taken as an additional evidence for the enolization of the thioketo group and the involvement of thioenol structure in bonding. The thioketo group bands are shifted to lower wavenumbers in the spectra of [Cu(PNTS)₂SO₄] and [Cu(IBTS)₂SO₄] indicating the participation of thioketo group in bonding.

The strong band at 1685 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in the spectrum of IBTS, is shifted to lower wavenumbers in the spectra of all the complexes except the copper sulphate complex, where it remains at the same position. This indicates that the carbonyl oxygen is taking part in coordination in all the complexes except the copper sulphate one. The infrared spectra of [Cu(PNTS)₂SO₄] and [Cu(IBTS)₂SO₄] show ν_3 and ν_2 bands for the sulphato group which indicate the presence of a chelating sulphato group¹¹.

The elemental analyses together with infrared studies suggest that PNTS acts as a bidentate and coordinates through NH and thioenol groups, while IBTS acts as a tridentate coordinating via NH, C=O and thioenol groups. In the copper

sulphate complexes of both IBTS and PNTS, the coordination proceeds through thioketo group only.

Magnetic and spectral studies: The magnetic moments (Table 1) and the electronic spectra have been used to decide the stereochemistry of the isolated solid complexes. The electronic spectra of the complex [Ni(PNTS-H)₂] show two bands at 15,700 and 21,200 cm^{-1} due to ν_2 and ν_3 transitions, respectively¹² which may suggest a square planar configuration around Ni(II) ion. The band at 13,200 cm^{-1} may be due to spin forbidden as reported by Jørgensen¹³ in square planar complexes containing sulphur ligands. The diamagnetic behaviour of Ni(II) complex prove the existence of a square planar geometry. Magnetic moments of low spin planar Co(II) complexes usually lie in the 2.1-2.9 B.M. range¹⁴. The complex [Co(PNTS-H)₂]H₂O falls in the above range, suggesting a square planar configuration around cobalt ion. The complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) derived from IBTS show magnetic moments similar to those reported for octahedral complexes¹⁵. The bands at 18,600 and 28,300 cm^{-1} in the complex [Ni(IBTS-H)₂]2H₂O are assigned respectively to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$, while the two bands at 8,800 and 16,200 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of [Co(IBTS-H)₂]2H₂O are assigned to $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(\text{F})$ and $^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(\text{P})$. Thus, the electronic spectra of both Co(II) and Ni(II) are in favour of octahedral geometry. All copper complexes of IBTS and PNTS showed a broad band with a maximum in the range 14,200-16,900 cm^{-1} . A shoulder has been observed at 17,300 cm^{-1} in the spectra of mono-ligand complexes derived from IBTS, beside the main band which support the presence of square planar configuration around Cu(II) ion¹⁶. The more intense bands in the ranges 30,600-36,900 and 20,000-24,400 cm^{-1} may be assigned as charge transfer, probably $d-\pi^*$ ¹⁷. The subnormal magnetic moment of the complex [Cu(PNTS-H)₂] may be due to spin exchange phenomena¹⁸, while the high magnetic moments in some Cu(II) complexes may be attributed to the

lowering of symmetry around Cu(II) ion¹⁹. The complexes of Cu(II) bromide derived from IBTS and PNTS show subnormal magnetic moments which may suggest a polymeric structure with halogen bridge as those reported earlier¹⁹.

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